

CoMPSeT: A framework to compare variants of Multiparty Session Types

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Abstract. Concurrent systems are often complex and difficult to design. Choreographic languages, such as Multiparty Session Types (MPST), allow the description of global protocols of interactions by capturing valid patterns of interactions between participants. Many variations of MPST exist, each one with its rather specific features and idiosyncrasies. Here we propose a tool – CoMPSeT – that provides clearer insights over different features in existing MPST. We select a representative set of MPST examples and provide mechanisms to combine different features and to animate and compare the semantics of concrete examples. CoMPSeT is open-source, compiled into JavaScript, and can be directly executed from any browser, becoming useful both for researchers who want to better understand the landscape of MPST, and for teachers who want to explain global choreographies.

Keywords: Multiparty Session Types, Operational Semantics, Animation Tools

1 Introduction

Many formalisms exist to describe communicating systems, including *Multiparty Session Types* and other choreographic languages. As a consequence of this diversity, many of these formalisms have small but important differences in expressiveness that are not always easy to grasp. For example, some systems cannot express pure interleaving in a local component, or assume that interactions are atomic, blocking both senders and receivers. Understanding the impact of these differences with concrete examples is also non-trivial. Moreover, the development and analysis of each of these systems pose a significant challenge, considering the multitude of flow executions and behaviours that must be understood in order to assert the absence of communication errors [1].

This paper focuses on Multiparty Session Types (MPST), a typing discipline that ensures message-passing processes adhere to a specified multiparty session protocol (session fidelity) [2] while ensuring communication safety (absence of errors) and deadlock-freedom (progress) as originally formulated by Honda et al. [3]. *Session Types* denotes a formalism capable of verifying correctness in concurrent programs, where the well-behaviour of a protocol can be asserted through the well-typedness of its participants. The *Multiparty* aspect generalizes

the earlier concept of *Binary Session Types* [4], which considered communications between only two parties.

Most works on MPST consider a global view of the session, given by a *global type*, and a local view of the session given by the *local type* of each participant. The local types can be seen as projections of the global type, and the global type as a combination of the local types. Local types can be used to type-check processes, whereas a well-typed process is guaranteed to follow a specific pattern of communicating actions. In this paper, we do not consider processes and focus only on the global and local types. Their semantics is described by how local types can mimic the evolution of well-typed processes.

Fig. 1: Master-workers protocol: message sequence chart (left), global type (middle), and a local type (right)

Consider our running example in Fig. 1, describing a master delegating work to two workers, which can stop working and inform the master in any order. A sequence diagram on the left is used to describe these interactions, using a special box `par` to capture parallel execution. Possible global and local types to describe this behaviour are presented on the right of the figure. Variations of our syntax (inspired by choreographic languages) are used by different authors, each supporting different constructors and different syntactic restrictions. Furthermore, some models for choreographies describe the behaviour of the global protocol explicitly, without composing the behaviour of its projections, yielding notions of *weak sequencing* [5] whereas some later actions that do not depend on earlier ones can be performed before.

Contributions

We decided to use a superset of this syntax, providing tools to identify the class of MPST that a given type belongs to, and to animate different semantics. More concretely, our core contribution is a prototype tool called `CoMPSeT` that:

- is available to be executed online at <https://telmoribeiro.github.io/CoMPSeT/>;
- uses an input language for the global type using a superset of choreographic operators;
- supports configuring how the language is interpreted, e.g., synchronous vs. asynchronous communication, or what constructs can be used;

- depicts the protocols using sequence charts;
- animates the different semantics, both step-by-step or by drawing the full state-space; and
- can compare how two semantics differ for the same session (via trace equivalence or bisimulation).

Organisation of the paper Sect. 2 introduces MPST, including its syntax, the notion of projection, and an overview of its semantics. Sect. 3 identifies different variations of MPST in the literature, describing a core set of features that are explicitly analysed by our tool. Sect. 4 describes our tool CoMPSeT, including implementation details and how to use it to compare different MPST. Finally, Sect. 5 concludes our paper and discusses future work.

2 MPST in a nutshell

This section summarizes a concise description of our MPST syntax and semantics, inspired mainly by Daniélou and Yoshida [6] and by Castagna et al. [7]. We include combinators from multiple sources, although not all are supported by all the semantics of MPST, which will be addressed in Sect. 3.

2.1 Global Types

Let \mathbb{R} be the set of all *participants*, ranged over by $\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{r}$; \mathbb{T} be the set of all *labels*, ranged over by \mathbf{t} ; and \mathbb{G} be the set of all *global types*, ranged over by G . The syntax of a global type G is given by the following grammar.

$$G ::= \mathbf{p} \rightarrow \mathbf{q} : \{\mathbf{t}_i ; G_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mid G_1 ; G_2 \mid G_1 \parallel G_2 \mid \mu X. G \mid X \mid (G)^* \mid \text{skip}$$

We preserve the global types' informal meaning from Cledou et al. [8] along with Jongmans and Proença [9], such that:

- $\mathbf{p} \rightarrow \mathbf{q} : \{\mathbf{t}_i ; G_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ specifies the **communication** of a label \mathbf{t}_i from the participant \mathbf{p} to the participant \mathbf{q} , followed by the global type G_i , for some $1 \leq i \leq n$. As an additional well-formedness requirement, we stipulate that **(1)** $\mathbf{p} \neq \mathbf{q}$ (i.e., no self-communications) and **(2)** the labels in \mathbf{t}_i must be pairwise distinct (i.e., deterministic continuations). Moreover, we write $\mathbf{p} \rightarrow \mathbf{q} : \{\mathbf{t}_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} ; G$ as a shorthand for $\mathbf{p} \rightarrow \mathbf{q} : \{\mathbf{t}_i ; G\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.
- $G_1 ; G_2$ specifies the **sequential composition** of G_1 and G_2 .
- $G_1 \parallel G_2$ specifies the **parallel composition** of G_1 and G_2 .
- $\mu X. G$ and X specifies a **recursive protocol** (guarded and bounded) achieved through the *fixed point* notation.
- $(G)^*$ specifies a **recursive protocol** (guarded) achieved through the *Kleene star* notation.
- *skip* specifies **sequence identity**.

Example 1. The global type $G_{\text{master-workers}}$ below captures the *standard master-workers protocol* from Fig. 1.

$$G_{\text{master-workers}} = \text{master} \rightarrow \text{worker}_A : \text{Work}; \text{master} \rightarrow \text{worker}_B : \text{Work}; \\ (\text{worker}_A \rightarrow \text{master} : \text{Done} \parallel \text{worker}_B \rightarrow \text{master} : \text{Done})$$

2.2 Local Types & Projections

Similarly to global types, local types are defined as:

$$L ::= \text{pq}!\{\mathbf{t}_i; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mid \text{pq}?\{\mathbf{t}_i; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mid L_1; L_2 \mid L_1 \parallel L_2 \mid \mu X.L \mid X \mid (L)^* \mid \text{skip}$$

The informal meaning of the local types is such that:

- $\text{pq}!\{\mathbf{t}_i; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ specifies a sending of a label \mathbf{t}_i from the participant \mathbf{p} to the participant \mathbf{q} , followed by the local type L_i , for some $1 \leq i \leq n$. Moreover, we write $\text{pq}!\{\mathbf{t}_i; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}; L$ as a shorthand for $\text{pq}!\{\mathbf{t}_i; L\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.
- $\text{pq}?\{\mathbf{t}_i; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ specifies the reception of a label \mathbf{t}_i expected by the participant \mathbf{q} from the participant \mathbf{p} , followed by the local type L_i , for some $1 \leq i \leq n$. Moreover, we write $\text{pq}?\{\mathbf{t}_i; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}; L$ as a shorthand for $\text{pq}?\{\mathbf{t}_i; L\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.
- the remaining local types follow closely from the global types

As discussed in Sect. 1, the local types are obtained through the *projection* of the global type by each participant. This notion is formalized in Fig. 2, which in turn is based upon the definition from Yoshida and Gheri [10].

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{skip}|_{\mathbf{p}} = \text{skip}; & \\ X|_{\mathbf{p}} = X; & \\ (\mu X.G)|_{\mathbf{p}} = \mu X.(G|_{\mathbf{p}}) & \text{if } \mathbf{p} \in \text{participants}\{G\} \\ (\mu X.G)|_{\mathbf{p}} = \text{skip} & \text{if } \mathbf{p} \notin \text{participants}\{G\} \\ (G)^*|_{\mathbf{p}} = (G|_{\mathbf{p}})^* & \text{if } \mathbf{p} \in \text{participants}\{G\} \\ (G)^*|_{\mathbf{p}} = \text{skip} & \text{if } \mathbf{p} \notin \text{participants}\{G\} \\ \mathbf{q} \rightarrow \mathbf{r} : \{\mathbf{t}_i; G_1\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}|_{\mathbf{p}} = \text{pq}!\{\mathbf{t}_i; (G_i|_{\mathbf{p}})\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} & \text{if } \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{p} \neq \mathbf{r} \\ \mathbf{q} \rightarrow \mathbf{r} : \{\mathbf{t}_i; G_1\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}|_{\mathbf{p}} = \text{pq}?\{\mathbf{t}_i; (G_i|_{\mathbf{p}})\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} & \text{if } \mathbf{q} \neq \mathbf{p} = \mathbf{r} \\ \mathbf{q} \rightarrow \mathbf{r} : \{\mathbf{t}_i; G_1\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}|_{\mathbf{p}} = \text{merge}(\{G_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}|_{\mathbf{p}}) & \text{if } \mathbf{q} \neq \mathbf{p} \neq \mathbf{r} \\ (G_1; G_2)|_{\mathbf{p}} = (G_1|_{\mathbf{p}}); (G_2|_{\mathbf{p}}) & \\ (G_1 \parallel G_2)|_{\mathbf{p}} = (G_1|_{\mathbf{p}}) \parallel (G_2|_{\mathbf{p}}) & \\ \text{undefined} & \text{otherwise} \end{array}$$

Fig. 2: Projection $G|_{\mathbf{p}}$ of a global type G to a participant \mathbf{p} , using auxiliary functions *participants* and *merge*

The function *participants* returns a set of all participants in a given global type G . The function *merge* is a partial function that combines a set of local types L_i into a single one, using a strategy that will depend on a *merge criteria*, which will be explained in Sect. 3.

Example 2. The three local types below correspond to the projections of the global type $G_{\text{master-workers}}$ from Example 1 for each of the three participants. This example does not depend on the implementation of *merge* since it has no branching and because we assume that merging a single local type returns the same local type.

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\text{master}} &= \text{masterworker}_A!Work ; \text{masterworker}_B!Work ; \\ &\quad (\text{worker}_A\text{master}?Done \parallel \text{worker}_B\text{master}?Done) \\ L_{\text{worker}_A} &= \text{masterworker}_A?Work ; \text{worker}_A\text{master}!Done \\ L_{\text{worker}_B} &= \text{masterworker}_B?Work ; \text{worker}_B\text{master}!Done \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Running projections asynchronously

The semantics of a global type G is given by the concurrent execution of all its projections.¹ This section describes only an asynchronous (operational) semantics that assumes a single unbounded queue of messages for each pair of a sender and a receiver. This and other semantics are implemented in our tool CoMPSeT, explained later in the paper.

We define a *multiparty session* (MS) M as a set of local types $\{L_p \mid p \in \mathbb{R}\}$, one for each participant of M . We also define a *configuration* as a pair $\langle M, b \rangle$, consisting of a MS and a buffer $b : (\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{T}^*$, mapping each pair of sender-receiver to a sequence of labels in \mathbb{T} . The main operational rules to evolve a configuration are presented below, to send and receive a message.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \text{pq}!\{t_i ; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mid M, b \cup \{\text{pq} \mapsto ts\} \rangle &\xrightarrow{t_k} \langle L_k \mid M, b \cup \{\text{pq} \mapsto t_k \cdot ts\} \rangle \quad (\text{snd}) \\ \langle \text{pq}?\{t_i ; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \mid M, b \cup \{\text{pq} \mapsto t_i \cdot ts\} \rangle &\xrightarrow{t_k} \langle L_k \mid M, b \cup \{\text{pq} \mapsto ts\} \rangle \quad (\text{rcv}) \end{aligned}$$

Above we write k to represent any value between 1 and n , and write $t_i \cdot ts$ to denote the concatenation of the label t_i with the sequence of labels ts . For simplicity, we omit the other rules, including notions of structural congruence.

Other variations of these rules exist, e.g., ignoring the order of the messages or imposing the sending and receiving to be atomic. These and other variability points will be discussed in the next section.

3 Family of MPST

We identify a set of variation points between similar formalisations of MPST with respect to their semantics and expressiveness, which we call *features*. For

¹ Often the projections are used to type processes, which in turn have an operational semantics. We do not define processes in this paper and present directly this semantics over local types.

example, the criteria used for merging branches during projection. These features are based on the *essential features* proposed by Bejleri et al. [11], discarding aspects related to the processes typed by local types, not covered in our analysis.

The features that we identify are used in CoMPSeT to help identify the impact of these variation points, and to better compare a wide range of formalisations of MPST found in the literature. Some possible extensions of this feature set are later identified in Sect. 5.

We define a *concrete semantics* to be the semantics of our syntax of MPST after selecting an explicit set of desired features. These features are categorised as follows.

- **Merge criteria:** details the implementation of the *merge* function (Fig. 2), describing how different branches regarding the communication between two participants should be projected into another non-communicating participant. We consider both a *plain merge* and a *full merge*, borrowing the nomenclature from Scalas and Yoshida [2]. Informally, the *plain merge* accepts the projected branching communication as being well-defined, only if the continuation is *the same* on all branches. Conversely, the *full merge* allows different continuations if they are "compatible" [10].
- **Communication models:** details the underlying communication system between the various participants. We consider a *synchronous model* where senders and receivers communicate in a lock-step, a *causal asynchronous model* that assumes an unbounded FIFO queue between each directed pair of participants, and a *non-causal* version that ignores the message order.
- **Parallel:** captures if the system supports a local notion of parallel composition, akin to the description in Sect. 1.
- **Recursion:** details if the system supports recursion. We consider two forms: either by using fix points or by using a Kleene star (denoting zero or more repetitions of a term in sequence).
- **Well-formedness requirements:** captures additional requirements that are sometimes imposed. As an additional well-formedness requirement for the parallel composition [6] we consider the notion of *well-channelled* as $\text{comm}(G_1) \cap \text{comm}(G_2) = \emptyset$, meaning distinct communications occur in distinct sub-protocols). The function $\text{comm} : \mathbb{G} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{T}}$ maps each global type to its communications, represented as triples $(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{t})$. Additional requirements concerning implementation choices will be incremented in the following Sect. 4.

We summarise a set of concrete semantics found in the literature in Table 1, indicating in the left column a paper using MPST and in the other columns the selection of features used in that paper. This table focuses on the formalisations presented in the papers which do not always coincide with the underlying tools. E.g., [9] defines *fixed point recursion*, but uses a Kleene star in the implementation. Similarly, other MPST tools assume tail-recursion (which can be reduced to the Kleene star).

Table 1: Features mapping – ✓(present) or ×(absent) or N/S (not in scope)

Papers	Merge criteria	Communication model	Parallel composition	Recursion	Well-formedness requirements
[10]	plain + full	synch.	×	fixed point	
[12]	plain	asynch. (causal)	×	fixed point	
[8]	plain	asynch. (causal)	✓	×	well-channelled
[9]	plain	asynch. (causal)	✓	fixed point*	well-channelled
[13]**	N/S	asynch. (non-causal)	N/S	N/S	N/S

The last row includes an example of a choreographic language that introduces properties not often present in MPST, since it uses channels that ignore the order of the messages, also seen in other publications on choreographic languages.

These differences are remarked as they pertain to potential divergent implementations, which constitute the subject of the subsequent section and will be revisited therein.

4 Comparing Multiparty Session Types - CoMPSeT

This section describes some implementation details of CoMPSeT and how it is used to compare concrete semantics of Multiparty Session Types through hot-swappable features, aimed at encouraging hands-on experimentation and visualization.

4.1 CAOS

CAOS [14] is a Scala framework for **computer-aided development of Structural Operational Semantics (SOS)**, designed to define, test, and visualize SOS. Its primary focus is directed towards choreographic languages and the teaching of operational semantics by enabling the use of web-based interactive tools for semantic experimentation. CAOS defines widgets, i.e., modular blocks of extendable functionality, which serve as the foundation of communication and interaction with the user.

The web-based frontend of CoMPSeT is built using the CAOS libraries, supporting the creation of all JavaScript elements and producing the web interface depicted in Fig. 3. The interface consists of a collection of widgets that can be either expanded (such as *Session* and *Message Sequence Chart* in Fig. 3) or collapsed (such as *Message Sequence Chart* and *Global* in Fig. 4). Clicking the title toggles between these two modes and reloads the widget. Several native builders of widgets were used to compute, e.g., syntactic checking, automata generation, trace reconstruction, and bisimilarity verification.

Fig. 3: CoMPSeT– screenshot of the web interface

4.2 Extending CAOS

The web animator has been augmented to incorporate the new *settings* widget, along with several associated methods. Settings enable users to modify parameters defined by developers through the use of checkboxes, which are initially stated on a settings tree. In essence, this extension increments CAOS twofold:

- The developer is now equipped to design widgets whose behaviour is dependent on the state of the tree. Prior versions required the creation of each widget independently to account for potential variations, frequently anticipating that certain subsets would fail or be disregarded under given inputs. Conversely, the extension would need local workarounds, thereby increasing the workload for the developer.
- Widgets are now subject to a condition determining if they are to be rendered on the web interface. This condition may be further influenced by settings to reduce the number of displayed widgets and therefore, condense the information displayed.

The associated methods enable the developer to interact with settings akin to Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These methods consist of getters, setters, general filters, and small operations allowing the native widgets to pattern match on settings. Additionally, the native widgets can now modify settings and, by proxy, other widgets.

4.3 Revisiting the MPST family

In CoMPSeT, the settings displayed on the web interface (Fig. 3) are directly associated with the features derived from Table 1. As a result, the previous

Fig. 4: Local types and corresponding local automata for a simple branching protocol (full merge) – concrete semantics regarding [10], here denoted as **Very-GentleIntroMPST**

method of dividing each system into subsets based on its semantic properties has been reversed to enable the reproduction of its concrete semantics through the flexible integration of various settings. Decisions concerning the former will produce diverse widgets, thus allowing the user to examine and visualize the resultant impact, with the exception of the **Message Sequence Chart** and the **Global** (type) (Fig. 3), whose behaviour is straightforward and is displayed regardless of setting manipulation.

Notice that in CoMPSeT, the syntax used for the receiving local type is given by $pq?\{t_i; L_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ where p is the subject of the action, hence the receiver, in contrast to the formulation stated in Sect. 2.1, where it would be the sender.

We follow this subsection explaining each setting in the web interface and how they relate to the aforementioned features.

Merge The projection of global types relies on the merge criteria (Fig. 2). Multiparty Session Types typically defaults to the *plain merge* [3,15] or *full merge* [16,17]. We adopted the definitions from Yoshida and Gheri [10], which in turn reference Honda et al. [3,15] for the *plain merge* and Ghilezan et al. [18] for the *full merge*. In the web interface, the decision over this implementation will yield the immediate result of generating the local types and their automata. (Fig. 4).

Comm Model This setting pertains to the foundational communication framework among the various participants. Upon selection, it produces a widget allowing users to systematically advance through the session, thereby reconstructing potential traces (Fig. 5). Additionally, an automata regarding the overall communication is also created (Fig. 6). Selecting multiple communication models

The screenshot shows the CoMPSeT interface with the following components:

- Session:** 1 m->w:TaskA || m->w:TaskB
- Settings:**
 - Merge
 - Plain
 - Full
 - Comm Model
 - Sync
 - Async (Causal)
 - Async (Non-Causal)
 - Recursion
 - Kleene Star
 - Fixed Point
 - Parallel
 - Extra Requirements
 - Well Branched
 - Well Channeled
- Message Sequence Chart:** Global, Locals, Local Automata, Local Compositional Automata - Asynchronous (Causal), Local Compositional Automata - Asynchronous (Non-Causal).
- Step-by-Step Asynchronous (Causal):** Trace: undo; Enabled transitions: m!TaskA, m!TaskB; State: m: (m!TaskA || m!TaskB), w: (w?TaskA || w?TaskB)
- Step-by-Step Asynchronous (Non-Causal):** Trace: undo; Enabled transitions: m!TaskA, m!TaskB; State: m: (m!TaskA || m!TaskB), w: (w?TaskA || w?TaskB)
- Async (Causal) vs Async (Non-Causal) - Bisimulation:**

```

Not bisimilar:
- after m!TaskA,m!TaskB
+ m: skip
w: (w?TaskA || w?TaskB) can do w?TaskB
+ m: skip
w: (w?TaskA || w?TaskB) cannot do τ*,w?TaskB

```

Fig. 5: Step by step and bisimulation comparison for a simple task delegation protocol – concrete semantics regarding [8], here denoted as **APIGenInScala3**, and a non-causal asynchronous communication

additionally generates a bisimilarity analysis for each pair (Fig. 5). This capability encompasses a synchronous [10] and incorporates two asynchronous implementations: causal and non-causal. The causal implementation adheres to the behaviour alluded to in Sect. 2.3, whereas the non-causal implementation employs multisets to integrate certain features from choreographic models [19,13].

Recursion This setting enables a permissible recursion implementation, if any, on the current session. If a session requires a form of recursion implementation but it is not allowed by the settings, an error message is displayed akin to Fig. 7. Consequently, enabling this setting results in the suppression of said errors concerning the presence of recursive constructs. Moreover, the Kleene star recursion follows the underlying tool implementation from [9].

Parallel This setting behaves similarly to **Recursion**. As such, enabling the parallel composition will result in the suppression of errors regarding the presence of the local parallel construct within the current session.

Fig. 6: Compositional automata for a simple branching protocol (plain merge) – concrete semantics regarding [12], here denoted as **GentleIntroMPAsyncST**

Fig. 7: Error in a master-worker recursive protocol – concrete semantics regarding [9], here denoted as **ST4MP**

Extra (well-formedness) Requirements To address session non-compliance with the proposed extra requirements, additional syntactic checks are established, defaulting to errors displayed similarly to the previous instances (i.e., **Recursion** and **Parallel**). However, in contrast with those cases, enabling extra requirements does not suppress errors. Instead, it enables the additional syntactic checks to evaluate the global type as to determine if it complies with the designated setting. Furthermore, the implementation of CoMPSeT incorporates a relaxed branching version, internally noted as $L_A + L_B$. This decision signifies a progressive step towards comprehensive support of choreographic languages in subsequent iterations. Consequently, an additional well-formedness criterion, *well-branched*, is essential to assert compatibility with Fig. 2, thereby ensuring the branching behaviour commonly expected from MPST.

The aforementioned instances, among additional examples, are accessible for experimentation at <https://telmoribeiro.github.io/CoMPSeT/>. The **Examples** section provides the attained concrete semantics to facilitate their comparative analysis, accompanied by a diverse array of basic sessions and integrations of the two elements as supplementary motivational instances.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Available Multiparty Session Types systems often support diverse implementations. However, their structured nature facilitates categorization and compartmentalization of essential *features* and their possible implementations into recognizable subsets (Table 1).

This paper introduces the CoMPSeT tool, a framework for comparing different semantics of Multiparty Session Types through hot-swappable features. This is accomplished utilizing CAOS, a Scala toolkit that provides interactive capabilities for choreographic languages. Furthermore, it has been extended to incorporate the novel concept of *settings*, thereby facilitating dynamic behaviour and the condensation of displayed information.

By categorizing core MPST properties and providing an interactive tool, CoMPSeT enables the exploration and analysis of both session and semantical variations. Our tool allows for the dynamic configuration of MPST semantics, automata visualization, manual trace reconstruction, and bisimilarity comparisons.

While CoMPSeT already supports a range of MPST features, several extensions could further enhance its usability and scope, such as:

- Further feature assimilation would widen the range of reproducible systems and enhance the resemblance of the concrete semantics to the source. Specifically, supplementary adoption of *choreographic features* would extend the scope of the tool allowing for comparisons between different global communication systems;
- Although the current web interface allows for comparison between multiple semantics through examples and hot-swappable combinations, settings could

be modified as to allow for at least two concrete semantics on screen for improved comparability. In fact, the current expectation for the settings extension is to incorporate this behaviour, which initiatives are currently underway;

- The MPST pipeline often focus on API generation [20,8] compliant with the original global type. Efforts could be employed to introduce this ability natively or position the tool as a foundational layer in a broader framework, enabling both the semantical comparison and yielding the usual practical results expected from MPST.

By continuing to develop CoMPSeT, we aim to ease the grasp of the theory behind MPST and the impact of different implementations.

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